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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF TREATMENT OF CONTAMINATED
ABDOMINAL SURGERIES IN TERMS OF WOUND BY
PRIMARY VERSUS DELAYED PRIMARY CLOSURE**¹Dr. Yasmeen Kamboh, ²Dr. Muhammad Zahid, ³Dr. Samreen Zafar¹International University of Kyrgyzstan²Govt Mian Nawaz Sharif Teaching Hospital, Yakki Gate, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this study was to compare two surgical techniques, primary closure and delayed primary in the postoperative complication of the wound in contaminated cases.

Study design: A comparative study of cases and controls.

Configuration and duration: In the West Surgical Unit of Mayo Hospital, Lahore for One year duration from July 2017 to July 2018.

Methodology: In this study, 33 patients aged 33, over 12 and under 65 years of age had different pathological conditions. Different closure methods, e.g. Primary and late closures were performed to reduce wound complications. All patients presented with urgency and received antibiotics. In the case of primary closure delay a regular bandage was applied. The following results were planned for 1, 3 and 6 months.

Results: The incidence of infection in primary closure wound was 60%, whereas in primary closure group 33% were postponed. The frequency of popping was 12% in the primary, while the primary group was delayed in the same way as an incision hernia was found 10% and 6.2%, respectively.

Conclusion: laparotomy wound delayed primary closure seems to be an effective method for wound closure of wound wound on laparotomy in less cases than in wound healing.

Key Words: Intramedullary abdominal surgery, wound infection, primary closure postponed.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Yasmeen Kamboh,**

International University of Kyrgyzstan

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Peritonitis has been one of the surgical emergencies since decades. It should be treated appropriately, and wound-related complications, such as wound infection, wound adhesions and incisional hernia, otherwise causes greatly increase in the morbidity and mortality of surgical patients. The history of surgery is as old as humanity, and wounds have been part of the wound because of accidents, wars, and surgical operations. its texture. In the case of abdominal surgery, if the peritoneal cavity is highly contaminated, sepsis of the wound is inevitable. Wound closure techniques are one of the factors responsible for the poor or good results of surgical operations in case of contamination. In practice, contaminated wounds are closed by primary closure of the skin (normal abdominal closure) or delayed primary closure. Delayed primary closure was developed 200 years ago and corresponds to skin and subcutaneous tissue closure after a few days. The appearance of granulation tissue after the procedure is usually from the fifth to the sixth day. This is due to normal biological healing events. The wound is open for several days. The combination of events will greatly reduce the incidence of infection and also have a less chance of bacterial colonization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This comparative study of cases was held in the West Surgical Unit of Mayo Hospital, Lahore for One year duration from July 2017 to July 2018. Alternatively, the patients were divided into two groups (33 in each group). There were 11 patients in each group with Perforated Appendicitis, duodenal and ileal perforations were included. To prevent wound infection and delayed wound healing proper wound treatment is necessary. In Group A, the primary closure of the skin was done while in Group B delayed primary closure was performed. All cases presented with urgency. The incisions used were midline or gravitational (then at some point they were Rutherford Morrison Incision). Wounds were contaminated or dirty and emergency laparotomy was performed. Antibiotics were administered in all cases. After the facial closure, the wounds were washed with normal saline. The primary closure of the cases was left unsutured to the skin and subcutaneous tissues, and was then normally bagged until 24 hours and then the appearance of the

granulation tissue (wound healing) of the dressing band equipped with a thin layer of saline that was examined on a daily basis for 24 hours and then the wound. When the granulation tissue was somehow completely exposed, the two superficial layers were closed on average 5 days after the operation. Cultures were taken in both groups and adequate antibiotics were given according to culture and sensitivity reports. If there is swelling in the rash and pus, there is a suspicion of wound infection, while the serosanguinosa wound secretion Rosacea is suspected of opening the wound. From the date of the operation planned to group two groups of 1, 3 and 6 months to check for any evidence of the incisional hernia of the visit.

Participation criteria

Patients older than 12 years in both sexes were included in this study, all cases were performed on emergency bases and contained contaminated peritoneal cavity. Patients with peritonitis perforation, perforation and ilial perforation, in addition to having a hollow viscose perforation. All patients receiving V antibiotics were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria

Patients who knew the risk factors affecting the wound healing (anemia, jaundice, diabetes mellitus, steroid treatment, etc.) were not included in the study. Similarly, patients who died after surgery and did not participate in follow-up visits were excluded from the study. Patients not taking antibiotics were excluded from the study. Patients with a history of traumatic injury were not included in this study. Patients older than 65 and under 12 years of age were excluded from the study.

RESULTS:

This study initially included 74 patients, 38 in A and 36 in group B, but after discharge, 5 patients did not participate in normal follow-up, so group B and 3 were excluded in the study of group 3. A. Postoperative 3 patients, group A and group B One patient died, so these patients were excluded from the study. Finally, 66 patients were included in each group. Frequency in accordance with different diagnostic entities is given in Table I.

The incidence of infection in group B was 30%, while the frequency of wound infections in group A was 80% in perforated appendicitis, perforation in duodenum was 70%, ileal perforation was 60%, and perforated appendicitis was 31% and 50% in duodenal perforation. When the B group was 0%, the frequency of opening was 7, the duodenum perforation was 15.39% and the group A ileal perforation was 10%, the perforated supplement was 10%, respectively. The perforation of the intestine was 7.69% and the group A ileal perforation was 20% and 7.69% and 10% respectively in group B. In Group A it is 12% overall, in Group B a total of 9%, while incisional hernia incidence was equal to the separation of the wound in both groups. There is no clear difference in terms of gender and in terms of wound in two groups. Finally, the statistical test applied to demonstrate significant value (p value). The difference between the two groups was

statistically significant in terms of wound infection with p value (0.02). Other complications such as wound separation; It was found that incisional hernia was not statistically significant between the two groups.

DISCUSSION:

Without peritoneal events, gentle healing is of great importance, as most of these wounds are dirty or dirty. In most cases, the infection of the wound is still the main cause of the failure of wounds. It is also associated with some other complications, such as wound dehiscence and cut hernia. In this study, the frequency of delayed wound healing, p value For example, complications in closure of the primary wound exceeded 67% and showed statistically significant results with a p value less than 0.05% in delayed primary closure.

The results of this study are comparable to some international and local studies. Cohen stated that the infection rate was 12% in primary closure and 48% in primary closure group. Similarly, Smilanch showed a primary infection rate of 3% in the primary closure group. In the Bender6 study, infections in the primary deferred closure group were only 2.8%. In another study by Bradfrod, wound infection was observed in only 2 patients in the primary deferred closure group. A similar study by Urssir8 showed 30.2% of the infection rate in delayed primary closure and a prevalence of only 2.1% in the primary closure

group. In contrast to this study, which detected a 60% infection rate in primary closure, 33% in total closure group grew by 49% in total. This study also contradicts the findings of a 10-20% infection rate reported previously in several studies such as Woods Kumzawa and Cruis. Incisional hernia after laparoscopy remains a serious problem. In Sittu16, while the incisional hernia rate was 1%, the primary closure in this study was 6.2% in the deferred primary closure and 10% in the primary. In a study by Mingolin, incisional hernia was higher in emergency situations than elective surgery.

Cells Involved in Wound Healing

CONCLUSION:

Delayed primary closure is a better approach to abdominal closure in case of emergency abdominal surgery. It has consistently improved results on primary closure of the skin in terms of postoperative complications such as wound infection, wound separation, cut hernia and suture abscess.

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